

DETERMINANTS OF EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN THE BUSINESS SECTOR PRIMARY CONSUMERS ON THE INDONESIA STOCK EXCHANGE

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to analyze and address the research gaps in various previous studies, as well as the phenomenon where Organizational Commitment functions as an inconsistent intervening variable in explaining Employee Performance. These issues are the considerations behind this study. This type of research is quantitative descriptive with the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis method in the LISREL application. The research objects used are employees in Primary Consumer Business Sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange with a total of 5 companies during 2024. The research population was 8,038 respondents with a sample size of 400. The results of this study can be explained that all exogenous variables in this study can explain their influence significantly and have a positive correlation with endogenous variables. These results are expected to assist management in organizing and maximizing its human resources.

Keywords: Transformational Leadership, Career Development, Organizational Culture, Organizational Commitment, Employee Performance.

INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

The fundamental capital of any company's development comes from its human resources (HR). Therefore, their quality must be developed and directed to achieve the company's desired goals. Human resources can be viewed from two perspectives: quality and quantity. Quantity encompasses the number of available human resources (HR) or employees, while quality encompasses the human resources' physical and non-physical capabilities, including intelligence and mental abilities, in implementing company development. So in the process of company development, human resource development is very necessary because the large quantity of Human Resources without being supported by good quality will be a burden on the development of a company, H.Y Ruyatnasih, et., al, (2012).

Problems regarding Human Resources (HR) currently cause many companies to fail, either due to the poor work results of the existing human resources in the company or other problems. This phenomenon describes that the Human Resources (HR) factor has an important role that also determines the success of a company. Therefore, the success of a company or organization is very much determined by the utilization of Human Resources (HR), namely people who provide energy, talent, creativity and enthusiasm for the company and play an important role in the company's operational functions, Faldian Putra Rahmanda, Djamhur Hamid, Hamidah Nayati Utami, (2013).

Human Resource (HR) development within an organization is a way to improve the quality of individuals, groups, and the organization as a whole, making them more effective. This program is necessary considering that everyone within an organization is constantly moving towards change. These changes are caused by both internal organizational dynamics and external factors or forces (the external environment). Technological developments, for example, have implications for job requirements. The gap between workers and evolving job demands means the need for increased professionalism in knowledge, skills, and attitudes, Iwan Ridwansyah, (2004).

The phenomenon of increasingly fierce competition among companies demands that companies further improve the quality of their human resources. In this regard, human resources within a company continue to play a crucial role as the primary driver of all company activities in achieving its goals, both to generate profits and to maintain its survival. Therefore, the success or failure of a company in maintaining its existence begins with the efforts of its employees to maximize effectiveness and efficiency, Suardi Yakub, et al., (2014). In other words, the performance of an organization or company is greatly influenced and even depends on the quality and competitive capabilities of its human resources. The company's goal in standardization or benchmarking is so that the human resources or workforce it obtains can truly work according to what the company wants. Therefore, human resources are the main key to making a company superior to other similar companies. This concept shows that human resources in every company are important because the determining factor for the success or failure of a company in achieving its goals depends on how the company can develop its capabilities both in developing knowledge, skills and the desire of employees to develop cooperation between various work units that carry out different activities, Dwi Wahyuni, et., al., (2014).

Human resources are one of the factors that must be well managed by a company. Human resource management must be carried out professionally to produce competent human resources that can ultimately improve individual and company performance. However, the key to successful management, especially for employees, is the leadership used by a leader. In the process of creating effective performance, leadership plays a crucial role (Tria Mondiani, 2012). Leadership is a key element in organizational effectiveness. Furthermore, it is clear that leadership is the central point and determines the policies of activities carried out within a company (Berg & Baron, in Anikmah, 2008).

Given the above, the quality of human resources must be improved to achieve desired company goals. One way to improve human resources is through improving employee performance. Furthermore, it is known that an employee will perform well if they have a strong commitment to their company. Commitment is an attitude that reflects employee loyalty to the company. Employees with high commitment are expected to demonstrate optimal performance. Someone who joins an organization is required to have commitment within themselves. Organizational commitment indicates the degree to which employees believe in and accept the organization's goals and desire to remain with the organization (Mathis & Jackson, 2006). Without employee commitment to the company, the company's plans and targets will be difficult to realize.

Employee commitment to the company can minimize turnover and absenteeism and is expected to improve their performance. The relationship between commitment and performance is positive. Previous and recent research supports a positive relationship between organizational commitment and expected outcomes such as high performance, low turnover, and low absenteeism (Luthan, 2011).

High organizational commitment to employees will drive employee performance regardless of the strategy implemented (Catherina Melina Taurisa & Intan Ratnawati, 2012). Therefore, companies need to consider the implications of their employees' organizational commitment as a requirement to support company activities amidst increasingly fierce competition. This is done by considering and responding to the interconnected factors that contribute to organizational commitment, ensuring that employees behave optimally, as employees are a key asset in determining the company's success. An employee's commitment to an organization faces a fundamental problem: different employees will have varying levels of commitment. High levels of organizational commitment in employees typically lead to higher performance and can simultaneously reduce absenteeism. Conversely, if an employee has a low level of commitment, their performance will also be low. Commitment is a variable that can regularly predict employee behavior at work, particularly absenteeism. Employee commitment is known as an attitudinal approach to the organization. Mowday et al. (2008) found that employee commitment has two components: attitude and intention to behave. Highly committed employees will accept almost all assigned tasks and responsibilities and feel a sense of loyalty and belonging to the organization. Highly committed employees will be concerned about the fate of their organization.

In research by Nani Irmaniyati (2007), organizational culture, leadership, individual competence, and organizational commitment have a positive and significant influence on manager performance, both partially and collectively. Regarding the relationship between transactional and transformational leadership and organizational commitment in creating job satisfaction among frontline employees, Mohammad Rizan (2005) found that transactional and transformational leadership, along with organizational commitment, influence job satisfaction. Regarding the influence of organizational culture, leadership, and work motivation on employee performance, Ode Zusnita Muizu's (2008) research found that organizational culture, leadership, and work motivation influence employee performance. Further research by Indra Budi Sumantoro (2012) found that superior leadership, organizational culture, and emotional intelligence influence job satisfaction and organizational commitment.

Other research findings on the influence of competence, commitment, and organizational culture on managerial role actualization and organizational effectiveness by Kusnendi (2006) found that competence, commitment, and organizational culture significantly influence managerial role actualization and organizational effectiveness. Different results in Dixon (2012), The relationship of organizational commitment and Transformational leadership use in project managers. That affective and normative commitment have a positive and significant relationship with transformational leadership; continuance commitment has no relationship with transformational leadership. Different results in Ismail (2011), that transformational

leadership and empowerment have a positive and significant relationship with organizational commitment. By Jong Hun Baek (2012), transactional and transformational leadership have a significant influence on organizational commitment.

Research conducted by Baek-Kyoo Jo (2012), Core self-evaluation and transformational leadership have a positive and significant influence on Organizational Commitment. Likewise, the results in Dunn (2012), Bill Luthon (2010), transformational leadership has a relationship with organizational commitment. Other results by Josep Chui (2007), career development has a positive impact on employee commitment. Other results by Ogaboh (2010), career advancement, career guidance and career opportunities have a significant effect on employee commitment. Likewise, by Sarabia (2002), there is a significant, positive relationship between participation in effective career development programs and calculative commitment. By Briscoe (2009), boundaryless, self-directed and value-driven as career components have a positive relationship with organizational commitment, while organizational mobility is negatively correlated with each type of commitment.

HYPOTHESIS

H₁: Transformational Leadership has an effect on Organizational Commitment.

H₂: Career Development has an effect on Organizational Commitment.

H₃: Organizational Culture has an effect on Organizational Commitment.

H₄: Transformational Leadership has an effect on Employee Performance.

H₅: Career Development has an effect on Employee Performance.

H₆: Organizational Culture has an effect on Employee Performance.

H₇: Organizational Commitment has an effect on Employee Performance.

Figure 1: Research Framework Model

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is a descriptive study using a quantitative approach with hypothesis testing. The subjects of this study were employees of companies in the Primary Consumer Business Sector listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. The total number of companies during 2024 was five, with the main issuers based on their largest assets being PT Indofood Sukses Makmur Tbk (INDF), PT Indofood CBP Sukses Makmur Tbk (ICBP), PT Gudang Garam Tbk (GGRM), PT HM Sampoerna Tbk (HMSP), and PT Sumber Alfaria Trijaya Tbk (AMRT). From these five issuers, a total of 8,038 respondents were obtained. The sampling technique in this study used probability sampling, which meets the requirements of the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method. Data analysis used the LISREL application with a minimum of 200 observations, according to Juliasri Amin (2021), Hair, Aderson, Tatham, and Black in Kusenendi (2005), and Joreskog and Sorbom (1988).

Furthermore, the researcher used a sampling technique by means of proportional random sampling, in determining the sample members, the researcher took representatives from each group in the population whose number was adjusted to the number of subject members in each group, to determine the minimum sample required if the population size is known, the Slovin formula can be used with the assumption that the level of sampling error that is tolerated is 5% (Sugiono, 2016):

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = sample size

N = population size, 8,038

e = sampling error rate, which is 5%.

The results of the sample size calculation are as follows:

$$n = \frac{8.038}{1 + 8.038 (0,05)^2}$$

$$n = 400$$

Operational Variables:

Table 1: Operational Variables of Transformational Leadership

Variables	Dimensions	Indicators	Items
Transformational Leadership is a leader who can change an organization by identifying the need for change, initiating a vision, and	Idealized Influence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing a vision and mission • Instilling pride • Maintaining trust and respect 	X1 X2 X3
	Inspirational Motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being enthusiastic about the task • Expressing ideas • Inspiring subordinates 	X4 X5 X6
	Intellectual Stimulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being creative in solving problems • Creating a conducive environment 	X7 X8

mobilizing commitment to this vision, Bass in Baek (2012)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing ideas 	X9
	Individualized Consideration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing personal attention • Helping others develop themselves • Treating each employee individually 	X10 X11 X12

Table 2: Operational Variables of Career Development

Variables	Dimensions	Indicators	Items
Career development is the effort to develop the skills and competencies needed for various career fields, award degrees and/or certification, and provide guidance and counseling. Salter (2008)	Career certainty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarity of employee career paths • Clarity of employee futures • Provision of training for new employees 	X1 X2 X3
	Career decidedness.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confidence in their careers • Career paths aligned with competencies 	X4 X5
	Career decision making self-efficacy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding career choice factors • Understanding career development as a process • Increasing self-knowledge (interests, abilities, influences, personal values) 	X6 X7 X8
	Career exploration.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness and self-understanding of the career chosen • Having the ability to pursue the career • Interest in continuing the career path 	X9 X10 X11
	Career indecision	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unclear career path • Anxiety about one's career • Fear of career commitment 	X12 X13 X14
	Career Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having a well-defined career plan • Understanding existing career paths • Having career goals 	X15 X16 X17

Table 3: Operational Variables of Organizational Culture

Variables	Dimensions	Indicators	Items
Organizational culture is a system of shared understanding held by members of an organization that distinguishes it from other organizations, Robbin (2009)	Inovation and Risk Taking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovative and creative ideas • Possess new innovations • Dare to take risks 	X1 X2 X3
	Attention to Detail	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Able to analyze problems well • Carry out work in detail • Have work accuracy 	X4 X5 X6
	Outcome Orientation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complete work on time • Carry out tasks effectively • Carry out tasks according to work procedures 	X7 X8 X9
	People Orientation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do work diligently • Motivated to be a good employee 	X10 X11
	Team Orientation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Able to collaborate with colleagues • Able to solve problems as a team • Teamwork oriented 	X12 X13 X14
	Agressiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage work to be precise and fast • Aggressive in supervision • Pay attention to employee work 	X15 X16 X17
	Stability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain good work stability • Enforce discipline among employees 	X18 X19

Table 4: Operational Variables of Organizational Commitment

Variables	Dimensions	Indicators	Items
An attitude that reflects an employee's loyalty to their company. Employees who have organizational commitment are those who have a strong desire to be a key member of their organization, have a strong will to work and strive for the organization's interests, and have faith in and acceptance of the organization's values and goals, Meyer and Allen in Luthan, (2011)	Affective Commitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proud of the company • Caring about the company's future • Happy to choose the company as a place to work 	Y1 Y2 Y3
	Continuance Commitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compliance with company policies regarding employees • Loyalty to the company • Alternative jobs 	Y4 5 Y6
	Normative Commitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compliance with company norms • The company is the best place to work. • Acceptance of all types of jobs 	Y7 Y8 Y9

Table 5: Operational Variables of Employee Performance

Variables	Dimensions	Indicators	Items
A record of the results of work or certain activities achieved during a certain period of time, Bernardin & Russel, (2010)	Quality Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compliance with the quality of work completed according to company standards • Completing assigned work tasks according to work quality standards 	Z1 Z2
	Quantity Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compliance with the quantity of work completed according to company standards • Exceeding quantity targets 	Z3 Z4
	Timeliness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Punctuality in completing work • Always avoiding delays 	Z5 Z6
	Cost Effectiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficient use of work facilities • Level of damage to work facilities 	Z7 Z8
	Need for supervision	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Able to complete work without close supervision • Maintaining work discipline without close supervision 	Z9 Z10
	Interpersonal Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level of interpersonal relationships at work • Ability to collaborate with coworkers 	Z11 Z12

RESEARCH RESULTS

A. Analysis of Research Variable Description

Table 6: Score Range and Categories

Score	Score Interval	Category
1	1,00-1,80	Very Low/Very Poor
2	1,81-2,60	Low/Poor
3	2,61-3,40	Fairly High/Fairly Good
4	3,41-4,20	High/Good
5	4,21-5,00	Very High/Very Good

Source: Zikmund, William G., et. al (2010)

Table 7: Hybrid Model Measurement Model Suitability – SEM

Indikator <i>Goodness of Fit</i>	Expected Size	Estimation Results	Conclusion
<i>Ukuran Absolute Fit</i>			
<i>Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)</i>	GFI > 0,90	0,959	Good Fit
<i>Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)</i>	RMSEA < 0,08	0,0751	Good Fit
<i>Ukuran Incremental Fit</i>			
<i>Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI)</i>	NNFI > 0,90	0,936	Good Fit
<i>Normed Fit Index (NFI)</i>	NFI > 0,90	0,930	Good Fit
<i>Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)</i>	AGFI > 0,90	0,942	Marginal Fit
<i>Relative Fit Index (RFI)</i>	RFI > 0,90	0,921	Good Fit
<i>Incremental Fit Index (IFI)</i>	IFI > 0,90	0,943	Good Fit
<i>Comparative Fit Index (CFI)</i>	CFI > 0,90	0,943	Good Fit

Source: Processed data

Figure 2: Hybrid Model (Full SEM) Standardized

Figure 3: Hybrid Model (Full SEM) t-Value

Table 8: Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis	Hypothesis Description	Path Coefficient/ <i>R</i> ²	<i>t</i> -value	<i>t</i> - Criterion	Test Results
H1	$H_0 = 0$ Transformational Leadership (KT) has no effect on Organizational Commitment (KO)	0,246	2,872	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted. Transformational Leadership (KT) has an effect on Organizational Commitment (KO)
	$H_a \neq 0$ Transformational Leadership (KT) has an effect on Organizational Commitment (KO)				
H2	$H_0 = 0$ Career Development (PK) has no effect on Organizational Commitment (KO)	0,486	3,496	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted Career Development (CPD) has an effect on Organizational Commitment (OC)
	$H_a \neq 0$ Career Development (PK) has an effect on Organizational Commitment (KO)				
H3	$H_0 = 0$ Organizational Culture (BO) has no effect on Organizational Commitment (KO)	0,348	3,249	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted Organizational Culture (BO) has an effect on Organizational Commitment (KO)
	$H_a \neq 0$ Organizational Culture (BO) has an effect on Organizational Commitment (KO)				

Hypothesis		Hypothesis Description	Path Coefficient/ R^2	t -value	t -Criterion	Test Results
H4	$H_0 = 0$	Transformational Leadership (KT) has no effect on Employee Performance (KP)	0,275	2,573	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted Transformational Leadership (KT) has an effect on Employee Performance (KP)
	$H_a \neq 0$	Transformational Leadership (KT) has an effect on Employee Performance (KP)				
H5	$H_0 = 0$	Career Development (PK) has no impact on Employee Performance (KP)	0,238	2,438	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted Career Development (PK) has an impact on Employee Performance (KP)
	$H_a \neq 0$	Career Development (PK) has an impact on Employee Performance (KP)				
H6	$H_0 = 0$	Organizational Culture (BO) has no effect on Employee Performance (KP)	0,362	3,127	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted Organizational Culture (BO) has an effect on Employee Performance (KP)
	$H_a \neq 0$	Organizational Culture (BO) has an effect on Employee Performance (KP)				
H7	$H_0 = 0$	Organizational Commitment (KO) has no effect on Employee Performance (KP)	0,312	6,438	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted Komitmen organisasional berpengaruh terhadap Kinerja pegawai
	$H_a \neq 0$	Organizational Commitment (KO) has an effect on Employee Performance (KP)				

Source: Processed data

Table 9: Summary of Test Results Between Latent Variables

No	Structural Path	Path Coefficient	t -Value	t -Criterion	Test Results
1	(KT) → (KO)	0,246	2,872	1.96	Significant
2	(PK) → (KO)	0,486	3,496	1.96	Significant
3	(BO) → (KO)	0,348	3,249	1.96	Significant
4	(KT) → (KP)	0,275	2,573	1.96	Significant
5	(PK) → (KP)	0,238	2,438	1.96	Significant
6	(BO) → (KP)	0,362	3,127	1.96	Significant
7	(KO) → (KP)	0,312	6,438	1.96	Significant

Source: Processed data

Sub-Structural Equation 1

$$KO = 0,246*KT + 0,486*PK + 0,348*BO, \text{ Error var.} = 0.167, R^2 = 0,833$$

$$\begin{matrix} (0.076) & (0.089) & (0.075) & (0.069) \\ 2,872 & 3,496 & 3,249 & 4.60 \end{matrix}$$

Sub-Structural Equation 2

$$\begin{array}{cccccc}
 KP = 0,275*KT + 0,238*PK + 0,362*BO + 0,312*KO, \text{ Error var.} = 0.158, R^2 = 0.842 \\
 (0.090) & (0.091) & (0.075) & (0.074) & (0.060) \\
 2,573 & 2,438 & 3,127 & 6,438 & 3.29
 \end{array}$$

B. Results

- H₁: Transformational Leadership has a significant effect and is positively correlated with Organizational Commitment.
- H₂: Career Development has a significant effect and is positively correlated with Organizational Commitment.
- H₃: Organizational Culture has a significant effect and is positively correlated with Organizational Commitment.
- H₄: Transformational Leadership has a significant effect and is positively correlated with Employee Performance.
- H₅: Career Development has a significant effect and is positively correlated with Employee Performance.
- H₆: Organizational Culture has a positive effect and is significantly correlated with Employee Performance.
- H₇: Organizational Commitment has a significant effect and is positively correlated with Employee Performance.

CONCLUSION

Career Development is the dominant variable in the Organizational Commitment variable of employees in Primary Consumer Business Sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, where the Organizational Commitment variable can successfully mediate and explain its influence on the research problem, namely Employee Performance.

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